

1. Introduction

In this study, composites incorporating two different matrices - UHMWPE GUR® 5113 and a urethane-based Shear Thickening Fluid (STF) DIC701N - were evaluated using impact tests at both low and high velocities. Two types of aramid fiber fabrics, Twaron® CT 608 and PT 900, were used in the composites under investigation. Test samples with 1 to 6 discrete fabric layers were prepared by compression molding and spread coating, respectively. In the compression molding method, samples were directly fabricated with the specified number of layers. In the spread coating method, the fabric was coated, then cut and stacked to obtain the desired number of layers. Preliminary low-velocity impact tests were first conducted using a CEAST Fractovis Plus drop impact tester, at an impact velocity of 4.429 m/s and an energy of 245.6 J, to provide an initial assessment of the composites' response. Subsequently, high-speed impact tests were performed in a custom laboratory setup employing a 5.5 mm caliber slug projectile, with a length of 11.8 mm and a mass of 2.74 g, fired via a compressed air system in accordance with the MIL-STD-662 F standard.

2. Materials

Reinforcements

Twaron® CT608 (Teijin)

- Plain weaves
- Areal density – 123 g/m²
- Yarn properties:
 - Strength at break – 148 N
 - Chord modulus – 100 GPa
 - Strain at break – 3.5 %

Twaron® PT900 (Teijin)

- Satin and plain weaves
- Areal density – 204,6 g/m²
- Yarn properties:
 - Strength at break – 225 N
 - Chord modulus – 89GPa
 - Strain at break – 3.45 %

Matrices

UHMWPE

- GUR® 5113 (Celanese)**
- Injection moulding grade
 - Average molecular weight – 3.7E6 g/mol
 - Tensile modulus – 750 - 800 MPa
 - Tensile stress at yield ≥ 17 MPa
 - Strain at break – 430 %

Dilatant compound DIC701N (Polianswer)

- STF (70 %) + Ethanol (30%)
- STF based on urethane chemical structure
- Liquid phase - unpolymerized urethane monomer
- Solid phase – polymerized particules

STF-Coated Fabrics (STFCF)

STF-coated fabrics (STFCFs) were prepared using the knife-over-air spread coating technique. The dilatant fluid was diluted to reduce its viscosity and facilitate proper application. To ensure coating on both sides, the fabric was flipped and the process repeated.

4. Low-velocity drop weight impact testing

Low-velocity impact tests were performed on neat fabrics (NFs), STF-coated fabrics (STFCFs), and composite laminates (CLs) using a CEAST Fractovis Plus drop-weight tester, following the ISO 6603-2 standard. Samples (140 × 140 mm) were clamped between circular jaws, with teeth machined on the upper jaw and matching grooves on the lower jaw, to provide interlocking fixation during testing. For each material type, two configurations were tested: samples composed of a single fabric layer and samples composed of four fabric layers.

Experimental Conditions

- Clamping force = 10 kN
- Hemispherical Impactor, Ø = 20 mm
- Impact Mass = 25.044 kg
- Drop Height = 1000 mm
- Impact Velocity = 4.429 m/s

Due to the different areal densities of the samples, the energy absorbed by the STFCFs and CLs was normalized with respect to their areal density, using the equation $E_n = \frac{E_a}{(1+x\%/100)}$, where E_n is the normalized absorbed energy (J), E_a is the absolute absorbed energy (J), and $x\%$ is the add-on percentage.

Results

- STF-based composites exhibited improved impact resistance compared to neat aramid fabrics. This enhancement is likely attributed to the shear thickening effect, which restricts fiber mobility and promotes stress transfer, thereby increasing the area involved in energy absorption.
- For CT 608, using UHMWPE as the matrix, reduced both absolute and normalized absorbed energy, likely due to excessive fiber impregnation leading to quasi-brittle failure. For PT 900, UHMWPE increased absorbed energy, but normalized gains were significant only with four fabric layers. This is presumably due to partial impregnation, which enables additional energy absorption mechanisms (e.g., matrix/fabric debonding, yarn stretching, and delamination).

5. High-velocity impact (Ballistic testing)

Ballistic tests were performed on neat fabrics (NFs), STF-coated fabrics (STFCFs), and composite laminates (CLs) using a setup developed in our lab. A 5.5 mm caliber ELR slug projectile was fired using a compressed air system, in accordance with the MIL-STD-662F standard. Samples (140 × 140 mm), consisting of one to six fabric layers, were clamped in a target-retaining frame featuring a 100 × 100 mm window. The frame included teeth machined into the upper part that fit into grooves in the lower part, preventing sample slippage. Each sample was secured using 12 screws.

Impact velocities:

CT608 (4 layers)
 $V_{50} = 204,73 \text{ m/s}$
 $V_{100} = V_{50} + 3\sigma = 210,3 \text{ m/s}$

PT900 (3 Layers)
 $V_{50} = 217,3 \text{ m/s}$
 $V_{100} = V_{50} + 3\sigma = 220,9 \text{ m/s}$

Results

3 of 4 STFCF samples not perforated

- Ballistic Limit (3 layers STFCF) ≈ Impact Velocity
- 20% - 40% reduction in aramid fabric

6. Conclusions

- ✓ Fabric impregnation by UHMWPE matrices plays a key role in low-velocity impact, where excessive impregnation leads to a reduced energy absorption. This effect was not observed under high-velocity impact, except when a single fabric layer was tested.
- ✓ Under high-velocity impact, excessive STF impregnation reduces fabric performance, likely due to a pronounced thickening effect that excessively limits fiber deformation, leading to premature fiber rupture. Shear rates are highest at impact point and decrease through the thickness, diminishing the thickening effect in deeper layers. This gradient allows greater energy dissipation, making STF-impregnated fabrics potentially more effective in the back layers by reducing back-face deformation.

7. References

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